

Demo: RALA-PSO, Intelligent Scheduling of Cloud-Native Applications

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Abstract—This demonstration presents a live, interactive showcase of RALA-PSO (Resource-and-Latency-Aware Particle Swarm Optimization) algorithm [1] [2] integrated within the MIRO orchestration platform [3] for intelligent cloud-native scheduling. Attendees will experience hands-on interaction with three algorithmic variants considering different fitness objectives through MIRO’s dashboard, observing live scheduling decisions and performance metrics integrated within a multi-domain infrastructure. The demo illustrates state-of-the-art swarm intelligence research applied to a real Cloud-Native solution, bridging the gap between algorithmic innovation and practical deployment.

Index Terms—Swarm Intelligence, resource scheduling, cloud-native, microservice orchestration, particle swarm optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

While RALA-PSO represents a novel algorithmic approach in swarm intelligence-based cloud-native scheduling, its practical deployment faces substantial complexity barriers requiring deep expertise in PSO parameters, fitness functions, and infrastructure integration. This demonstration presents how MIRO (Multi-Domain Intelligent Resource Orchestrator) [3] bridges this innovation-to-implementation gap, leveraging RALA-PSO [1] [2] from theoretical research into accessible, enterprise-ready solutions.

RALA-PSO extends classical PSO with five key enhancements: greedy probabilistic initialisation, circular search space, multi-criteria fitness function, heuristic-based cluster classification, and adaptive weights. MIRO addresses Cloud-Native resource management across heterogeneous, multi-domain infrastructures spanning on-premises, cloud, and edge environments. The demonstration showcases MIRO using three algorithm variants: **RA-PSO** (resource-aware), **RALA-PSO** (resource-and-latency-aware), and **RA2LA-PSO** (resource-latency-location-aware) as the intelligent scheduling backend for optimising the placement of cloud-native applications across multi-domain infrastructure.

Experimental evaluations using the Alibaba Cluster TraceV2018 dataset show that RALA-PSO outperforms state-of-the-art algorithms (MOPPSO-CMS and ACO-CMS [4]), achieving $1.8\times$ – $2.36\times$ lower network overhead and up to $212\times$ faster execution while maintaining comparable resource utilisation efficiency [1] (Figure 1). Building on these results, this

demonstration focuses on how such optimisation capabilities can be made accessible for enterprise deployment through intuitive, user-friendly interfaces.

Fig. 1. Normalised network transmission overhead cost incurred when dependent components are placed further apart across clusters. Lower values indicate better performance.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

MIRO’s distributed orchestration architecture leverages a microservices-based design built upon Kubernetes, Cluster API, Liqo, Grafana, and Thanos technologies. The platform operates across three distinct infrastructure layers: on-premises data centers, public cloud environments (AWS, Azure, GCP), and edge computing nodes. This multi-domain approach enables RALA-PSO to optimally distribute workloads based on latency requirements, resource availability, and location constraints.

The RALA-PSO integration operates through MIRO’s intelligent scheduling engine, which continuously ingests real-time telemetry data, including CPU utilisation, memory consumption, network latency metrics, and storage I/O performance across all managed clusters. This telemetry feeds directly into the PSO fitness function calculations, ensuring scheduling decisions reflect current infrastructure conditions rather than static assumptions.

This demonstration considers three key algorithmic variants through a pluggable scheduler interface: RA-PSO optimises purely for resource efficiency, RALA-PSO incorporates net-

work latency considerations for distributed applications, and RA2LA-PSO adds geographical location awareness.

III. LIVE DEMONSTRATION WORKFLOW

The live demonstration will enable attendees to interact with MIRO’s dashboard (Figures 2 and 3) and define application and deployment requirements, observing in real-time how RALA-PSO incorporates these inputs into its scheduling decisions across a multi-domain infrastructure. A dedicated algorithm selection interface (Figure 4) enables real-time switching between RALA-PSO variants and baseline schedulers, allowing users to easily compare the impact of different scheduling approaches. The demonstration also aims to showcase and discuss how a distributed orchestration architecture built upon technologies such as Kubernetes, Cluster API, Liqo, Grafana, and Thanos facilitates unified management across on-premises, cloud, and edge environments, continuously supplying the algorithm with live telemetry and operational metrics used directly in its scheduling decisions.

The demonstration setup includes a large table with power connections and Wi-Fi access, a 55-inch monitor accompanied by a secondary display, and a laptop workstation, used to host and showcase the MIRO dashboard and the RALA-PSO algorithm in action. A 30×40-inch poster provides an overview of the system architecture, RALA-PSO and scheduling workflow.

Fig. 2. MIRO Dashboard showing live infrastructure.

Fig. 3. MIRO Application builder used to define application requirements and constraints.

Fig. 4. MIRO Dashboard RALA-PSO scheduling decisions.

IV. CONCLUSION

This live demonstration showcases how RALA-PSO goes from research innovation into a practical enterprise application through MIRO’s interactive orchestration platform. Attendees will experience firsthand the power of swarm intelligence-based scheduling by dynamically switching between three algorithmic variants (RA-PSO, RALA-PSO, RA2LA-PSO) and observing real-time scheduling decisions across multi-domain infrastructure. The demonstration emphasises accessibility and usability, enabling practitioners to leverage state-of-the-art optimisation without deep algorithmic expertise. By providing hands-on interaction with live telemetry, performance metrics, and comparative analysis between scheduling approaches, this demonstration bridges the critical gap between academic research and industry adoption, illustrating how innovative algorithms can be seamlessly integrated into existing cloud-native workflows to deliver measurable operational improvements.

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